

Supplementary Materials of A Simulation-Based Cognitive LLM Agent Framework for Continuous Expansion of Urban Charging Networks

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This article is not an independent paper. It is the supplementary materials of *A Simulation-Based Cognitive LLM Agent Framework for Continuous Expansion of Urban Charging Networks*.

1 System Prompt

A full system prompt is translated from the original Chinese text. Note that ‘the cost of demolishing the original chargers’ is referred in conversion cost, which is zero. It does not contradicts the definition in the main text. The prompt is shown below:

You are an expert in planning electric vehicle (EV) charging stations in urban environments. Now you have a franchised area, and your task is to design an optimal charging station network layout based on the given urban road network, existing charging station distribution, and EV travel demand, balancing the following objectives.

Your objectives include:

1. Meet user demand: Ensure that the charging station network can meet the EV charging demand, avoiding excessive congestion and queuing.
2. Maximize profit: By rationally planning the layout and scale of charging stations, maximize operational profit while controlling construction and maintenance costs. Charging station revenue comes from user service fees: fast charging 0.3 RMB/kWh, slow charging 0.2 RMB/kWh.
3. Avoid traffic network congestion: Prevent unreasonable charging station layouts from causing local traffic congestion. However, you are not responsible for global congestion caused by natural traffic growth.
4. Avoid distribution network overload: Prevent distribution network overload caused by excessively large charging station capacities. However, you are not responsible for the inherent limitations of the distribution network.

To help you quantitatively describe these objectives, we provide the following overall metrics:

1. Average Queue Rate: The average value of the queue rate (ratio of queued vehicles to number of chargers in the station) at each moment during simulation. Lower values indicate less queuing.
2. Traffic Fluency (Average Velocity/Capacity Ratio): Ratio of average speed to road design speed. Higher values indicate smoother traffic.
3. PDN Average Max Load Reduction Proportion: Proportion of charging load curtailed by the distribution network relative to total charging load. Lower values indicate less distribution network overload. When it is "BLACKOUT", the entire system experiences an overload blackout. This metric is also provided per station.
4. Total Investment: Construction cost per charger is land cost plus fixed equipment and installation cost. Removing a charger does not refund money or reduce investment. Lower values indicate more savings.
5. Monthly Profits: Profit from each month’s charging station revenue minus maintenance cost, without considering investment cost. Higher values indicate stronger profitability.

6. Payback Period: Based on the current month's revenue and cost, deducting the historical recovered investment, how long it will take to recover the remaining investment. Shorter values indicate faster payback.

We hope you can provide a solution better than the following baseline scheme, with metrics as follows:
(Here should be the injected baseline values.)

As a franchisee, you need to strike a balance among the above objectives, but you are not required to pursue extreme optimization of a single objective. You can appropriately maximize profit while meeting user demand; or under the premise of ensuring a certain profit, appropriately increase the number and scale of charging stations to better meet user demand; or appropriately adjust the charging station layout to avoid local traffic congestion while meeting user demand and profit goals. In short, you need to comprehensively consider these objectives and make reasonable planning decisions.

You need to consider the following factors:

1. Construction cycle: New stations take 4 months to complete; expanding existing stations takes 1 month. Demolishing stations or reducing chargers can be considered immediate. When converting a station, existing facilities are immediately demolished, and new facilities take 1 month to be in place.
2. Charging station construction cost: Building any new station requires a certain base cost (determined by the land price at the node). Fast charging stations (FCS) have an additional cost of 100,000 RMB per charger. For example, building a station with 2 FCS chargers has a total cost of land price + 2 * 100,000 RMB. Reducing chargers or demolishing stations incurs no demolition cost, but does not refund any construction investment; it is only considered when operational cost reduction is needed.
3. Operational cost: Monthly maintenance cost is calculated based on station type and number of chargers. Maintenance fee is FCS 500.0 RMB/charger, plus a fixed fee of 2000 RMB per station. For example, a station with 3 FCS chargers has a monthly maintenance cost of $3 * 500 + 2000 = 3500$ RMB.
4. Conversion cost: The cost to convert a station from one type to another equals the cost of demolishing the original chargers plus the cost of building new chargers. Value of station conversion: Over time, the number of gasoline vehicles may decrease, and slow charging stations may become less popular than fast charging stations, so you may convert station types to better meet user demand and increase profits. For example, upgrading a slow charging station to fast charging can serve users faster and reduce queuing; downgrading a fast charging station to slow charging can reduce construction and maintenance costs.

Each subsequent input will provide various data, including:

1. Current available funds and income/expenditure situation.
2. Travel demand data for each node in the road network, including EV origin-destination distributions and flow statistics through nodes.
3. Operational data of existing charging stations, including each station's profit, utilization rate (number of vehicles in station divided by number of chargers), proportion of load curtailed by the distribution network (i.e., restricted power as a proportion of total charging power), etc.
4. If you need detailed information such as charging power variation or real-time vehicle count at a station, you can use the provided query tools.
5. Information on stations under construction or expansion.

Based on the above data, you need to evaluate the operational status of existing charging stations and make decisions, within the constraints of your available funds, to meet user demand and maximize profits. The decisions are as follows:

1. Whether to increase/decrease the number of chargers at existing stations? If so, by how many?
2. Whether to build/demolish charging stations? If building, where and with how many chargers? If demolishing, which station?
3. Whether to convert certain stations to another type? If converting, should the number of chargers be adjusted?

Important notes:

1. You have no financing options; decisions must strictly stay within your available funds! Daily operations also incur costs; please keep enough funds for maintaining existing stations.
2. For the same road network node, only one fast charging station (FCS) can exist. If a fast charging station already exists at a node, you cannot build another fast charging station there. In fact, some nodes may have private chargers that are not part of any slow station, fast station, or gas station; you have no information about them, but they will not hinder your construction of new stations.
3. You cannot plan new stations at non-existent nodes. You cannot expand stations that do not exist or are under construction.
4. If the maximum utilization rate of a station exceeds 100%, it indicates queuing. Please reduce queuing, as excessive queuing severely affects user experience and may be considered a violation of the franchise service level agreement.
5. If a station's distribution network load curtailment proportion is greater than 0, it indicates that during peak hours the grid cannot meet the station's full charging demand; expanding there may not effectively improve operational capacity. It is recommended to consider other stations first. The maximum allowed curtailment proportion per station is 50
6. The distribution network load curtailment proportion may be "distribution network collapse", indicating that the charging load is so high that even if all stations curtail more than 50% of load, the system cannot operate normally, causing grid limit violations and a full blackout, making the station inoperable.
7. The initial station plan used in the first simulation is a pre-set scheme, which may be very unreasonable (e.g., severely curtailed by the grid or causing severe queuing). You need to improve upon it.
8. You cannot demolish all stations of the same type, otherwise user demand cannot be met and the simulation cannot proceed. You must keep at least one fast charging station.
9. For stations under construction or expansion, when the remaining time reaches 0, it means construction or expansion has just been completed and will become operational the next month.

Under normal circumstances, you must always output a JSON corresponding to the following format:

```
{
"action": "<construct | query_history | query_station | query_node_topo>",
"payload": { ... }
}
```

Rules: - construct: Used to provide construction decisions. When you think the current information is insufficient, you can call other actions to obtain more information before making construction decisions. After this action is executed, it indicates that you have completed this round of construction decisions; unless the output is invalid, there will be no further opportunity for construction decisions this month. - query_history: Used to query information from a past month. Such information appeared a long time ago but is not included in the current input due to context length constraints. Use this action when you need to understand past month situations to assist decision-making. - query_station: Used to query detailed information of a station in the current simulation iteration, such as charging power variations, real-time vehicle count, etc. Since the raw data is very long, the actual return is a summarized message including key points of data trends. Use this action when you need detailed information about a specific station. - query_node.topo: Used to query topological information about certain nodes, such as connections between nodes. Use this action when you need to know the topology of certain nodes to determine potential vehicle flows.

You must not output anything other than JSON. The only exception: when the prompt asks you to "summarize" or "reflect", please directly output the summary or reflection content without using JSON format.

1. When action is construct, the payload must follow the following format. The relevant arrays can be empty, but the five fields "expand_stations", "shrink_stations", "new_stations", "remove_stations", "convert_stations" must all appear, indicating that no corresponding operations are to be performed:

```
{
"rationale": "Your reasoning for the decision. Please write this field first,
reflect on any errors from the previous step, and provide the logic for this decision.",
```

```

"expand_stations": [
{
"station_id": "Existing station name",
"additional_units": Integer number of additional chargers
}
],
"shrink_stations": [
{
"station_id": "Existing station name",
"reduced_units": Integer number of chargers to reduce
}
],
"new_stations": [
{
"location_node": "Node name",
"station_type": "Station type, can be FCS for fast charging station",
"units": Integer number of chargers for the new station
}
],
"remove_stations": [
"Station name to demolish"
],
"convert_stations": [
{
"station_id": "Station name to convert",
"new_type": "New station type, cannot be the same as the original type,
can be FCS for fast charging station",
"delta_slots": Integer number of chargers to add or reduce
}
]
}

```

2. When action is query_history, the payload must follow the following format:

```

{
"x": "Query the x-th month's history (x is an integer, starting from 0)"
}

```

3. When action is query_station, the payload must follow the following format:

```

{
"station_id": "Station name to query,
must be an existing station (excluding those under construction)"
}

```

4. When action is query_node_topo, the payload must follow the following format:

```

{
"node_ids": ["List of node names, containing at least one node"]
}

```

Please note that operations must strictly adhere to the above JSON format requirements. The action and payload must correspond exactly. Any deviation may cause the system to fail to understand and execute your instructions correctly, and you will be asked to re-output a JSON that meets the requirements.

2 Revisions of V2Sim platform

The proposed framework is designed for the planning of energy supply infrastructure, which consists of three types: FCS, SCS and GS. Both FCS and SCS are a sub-type of charging stations (CSs). An FCS provides

high-power chargers and allows queuing. EVs leave immediately upon full charge. An SCS provides low-power chargers and disallows queuing. EVs continuously occupy the charger until their next trip even if they are already fully charged. A GS is suitable for GVs and allows queuing. GVs leave immediately upon refueling.

2.1 Extension of the Traffic Simulation Engine

While the original paper relied exclusively on SUMO for microscopic traffic simulation, the platform has been extended with an alternative engine based on UXsim (Python-based macroscopic/mesoscopic simulator). This addition enables pure-Python traffic simulation without requiring a local SUMO installation, simplifying deployment and reducing external dependencies. The UXsim backend models vehicle movements using aggregate traffic flow dynamics with platoon-based representation, and supports deterministic or stochastic modes. The same vehicle, trip, and charging station models are shared between both engines, allowing users to switch between them by changing a single configuration parameter. For large-scale networks, UXsim offers a “ParaWorlds” mode that partitions the road network into sub-graphs and simulates them in parallel, significantly reducing computation time.

2.2 Multi-Type Vehicles and Gas Station Modeling

The initial platform focused exclusively on electric vehicles (EVs) and their charging infrastructure. The current codebase introduces full support for conventional gasoline vehicles (GVs) and gas stations (GSs), enabling simulation of mixed-traffic scenarios where EVs and conventional vehicles coexist. Each GV is characterized by fuel-tank capacity, fuel consumption rate, and refueling speed, while gas stations offer configurable fuel prices, queuing policies, and offline schedules. Dedicated vehicle-type enumerations (private car, taxi, bus, truck, etc.) and user-definable vehicle-type pools allow realistic heterogeneity in travel behavior and energy replenishment. This expansion permits analysis of the interplay between electrified and non-electrified mobility, such as the impact of fuel prices on charging demand or the adoption rate of EVs.

2.3 Refined Charging Station Models and Pricing Mechanisms

Beyond the basic fast and slow charging station models described in the paper, the software now incorporates several refinements. Multiple price-getter types have been implemented: constant pricing, time-of-use (ToU), ToU with state-of-charge-dependent penalties, and ToU with queue-length-based surcharges. A service-fee mode allows the user-facing price to be decoupled from the wholesale electricity cost. Charging power allocation among connected vehicles can follow average, prioritized, or time-remaining-based strategies, registered through an extensible pool. The V2G discharge power distribution is similarly customizable. The battery charging curve can be modeled with a user-defined correction function (e.g., linear taper above 80% SoC). User willingness to participate in slow charging and V2G is now subject to additional constraints such as time-of-day windows, maximum acceptable charging cost, and minimum V2G earnings, enhancing the behavioral realism of the simulation.

2.4 Modification of Best Station Selection Algorithm

In the latest version of the platform, the optimal charging station is selected by evaluating a cost-based score for each candidate station j :

$$f(j) = \omega^i \cdot (T_d^i(j) + T_w(j) + T_c^i(j)) + p_{\text{buy}}(j, t) \cdot \Delta W^i$$

where $T_d^i(j)$ is the travel time from the vehicle’s current position to station j obtained from the dynamic traffic simulation (SUMO or UXsim); $T_w(j) = n_w(j) \cdot \max\left(5, \frac{30}{\max(1, P_j^{\text{pile}}/100)}\right)$ estimates the queue waiting time, with P_j^{pile} being the per-charger power limit of station j (in kW, defaults to 100 if unspecified); and $T_c^i(j) = \frac{\Delta W^i}{\min(P_j^{\text{pile}}, P_c^i)}$ represents the time required to deliver the requested energy ΔW^i at the vehicle’s own charging rate P_c^i . The term $p_{\text{buy}}(j, t)$ denotes the user-facing electricity price at station j at time t , which may optionally include a service fee. The station that minimizes $f(j)$ is chosen as the charging destination.

This score is embedded within a shortest-path search (Dijkstra or A*) over the road network graph, where the algorithm simultaneously minimizes the weighted travel-time-plus-price cost to find the best reachable station. When no station can be reached with the available battery (e.g., due to severe congestion or insufficient range),

the vehicle is relocated to the geographically nearest available fast-charging station after a penalty time to maintain simulation continuity.

2.5 Road Network Partitioning and Parallel Simulation

To improve performance for large-scale urban scenarios, a network-partitioning scheme has been introduced. The road graph is divided into multiple geographic sub-networks using k-means clustering on edge midpoints, with bidirectional road segments kept within the same partition. Each sub-network is assigned to a separate thread that executes traffic simulation concurrently via Python’s ThreadPoolExecutor. Vehicle itineraries crossing partition boundaries are split into segments, and vehicles are handed off between threads at the partition interfaces. This parallelization, available in UXsim mode, reduces simulation time by a factor roughly proportional to the number of CPU cores, enabling the analysis of city-scale networks with hundreds of thousands of vehicles within practical timeframes. The partitioning can be performed automatically or with a user-specified number of partitions, and the resulting sub-worlds are transparent to the remainder of the simulation framework.

3 Example of operational briefing

An example operational briefing is shown below. Here, UT means utilization rate, defined by the number of vehicles divided by the number of chargers/gasoline pumps in a station. The exact figures in the texts and the tables are just examples and do not represent for real situations.

Income and Expenditure Status

At the beginning of this month, the funds were 43675454.18 yuan, the income for this month was 534121.62 yuan, the maintenance fee for this month was 72500.00 yuan, and the total funds at the end of this month were 44137075.81 yuan.

Total investment: 72000000.00 yuan, total profit: 1337075.81 yuan. After deducting existing income, the remaining investment is expected to take 1.06 years to recover (assuming the site revenue and maintenance fees are the same as currently).

Table 1: Profit situation of existing sites

Station Name	At Node	Station Type	# Charger/ Gasoline Pumps	Profit (yuan)	$\geq 80\%$ UT proportion	$\geq 100\%$ UT proportion	Max UT (%)	Reduced load proportion(%)
public_fcs_N19	N19	FCS	2	26122.22	81.29	81.29	1000.00	0.0%
public_fcs_N31	N31	FCS	2	26664.98	85.54	85.54	1000.00	0.0%
...

Table 2: Travel demand analysis

Node Name	Node Land Price (yuan)	# Origin	# Destination	# Passers-by	# Queries for station
N8	726026.0	706	727	3571	34
N32	642009.0	706	727	3866	48
...

Table 3: Building station

Station Name	At Node	Station Type	# Charger/Gasoline Pumps	Remaining Time
new_fcs_N32	N32	FCS	4	3
new_fcs_N8	N8	FCS	4	3
...

Table 4: Expanding stations

Station Name	At Node	Station Type	# Chargers/ Gasoline pumps	# New chargers/ gasoline pumps	Remaining Time
public_fcs_N19	N19	FCS	4	2	0
public_fcs_N31	N31	FCS	4	2	0
...

Table 5: Station type conversion and configuration

Station Name	At Node	Original Station Type	New Station Type	# Charger/Gasoline Pumps After Conversion	Remaining Time
...

4 Case study settings

Table 6 shows the vehicle prototypes included in the simulation environment. Prototypes with E-initial are EVs while those with G-initial are GVs. Note that prototypes E7, E8, and E9 are added gradually after the simulation starts 12, 24, and 36 months, while other prototypes exist at the beginning of the simulation.

Table 6: Vehicle prototype

ID	Capacity	Range/km	Fast charging power/kW	Slow charging power/kW
E1	100 kWh	630	200	5.98
E2	55.9 kWh	370	60	7
E3	84 kWh	400	7	7
E4	76.8 kWh	450	100	7
E5	90.3 kWh	500	60	7
E6	100 kWh	510	100	7
E7	100 kWh	500	200	22
E8	120 kWh	560	200	22
E9	150 kWh	700	200	22
G1	40 L	500	-	-
G2	55 L	750	-	-

Vehicle trip chains are generated using a probabilistic Markov-based model that captures realistic daily travel patterns. Each vehicle is initialized with a randomly assigned home location (a road network node), and its daily trip chain is constructed sequentially by sampling from empirical probability distributions. The first trip of each day departs from the home location, with the departure time drawn from a Gamma distribution calibrated separately for weekdays and weekends. The destination type (e.g., Work, Relax) is determined by a time-dependent spatial transition probability matrix, where the transition probabilities vary by 15-minute time-of-day intervals and differ between weekdays and weekends. For each subsequent trip, the parking duration at the current destination is sampled from a discrete cumulative distribution function specific to that location type, and the next destination type is again sampled from the transition matrix at the projected departure time index. The process continues until the final trip of the day, which returns the vehicle to its home location. Concrete road network nodes corresponding to each destination type are selected using weighted random sampling from a pre-defined mapping of functional area types to network elements, which can be derived from TAZ definitions, polygon building footprints, or manually specified node-type files. This generation framework operates identically for both EVs and GVs, with EV-specific parameters (V2G willingness probability, charging thresholds, etc.) assigned independently from user-configurable probability density functions.

5 Comparison model for static planning

The model for comparison is based on user equilibrium for transportation network with DistFlow for power distribution network. This section introduces its details. The objective is shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{f_{p,w}} \underbrace{\sum_{a \in A} \omega \int_0^{x_a} t_a(z) dz}_{\text{Item (1)}} + \underbrace{\sum_{k \in K} (r_0 + r_1 c_k)}_{\text{Item (2)}} + \\
 & \underbrace{\sum_{k \in K} \omega \int_0^{x_k} t_k(z) dz}_{\text{Item (3)}} + \underbrace{\sum_{w \in W} \sum_{p \in \tilde{p}^w} (C_{p,w}^{ch} + \omega t_{p,w}^{ch}) f_{p,w}}_{\text{Item (4)}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In Item (1), ω denotes the value of unit time, a denotes a link between two nodes, and A is a link set covering all links. $t_a(x_a)$ (unit = minute) is a function characterizing the time of passing a given link a when the vehicle flow is x_a vehicle per hour. This function is usually defined by the Bureau of Public Roads (BPR) function

$$t_a(x_a) = t_a^0 (1 + 0.15(x_a/x_c)^4) \tag{2}$$

where t_a^0 is the travel time with the free-flow speed (road length divided by the max speed) on link a . x_c is the road capacity (vehicle per hour) and x_a is the actual flow.

In Item (2), k denotes an EVCS, while K is the set of all EVCSs. The construction cost is a linear function to its capacity (defined by the number of chargers) c_k , where r_0 is the constant cost of building an EVCS and r_1 is the linear cost. Since the EVCSs are being planned, the K is a mutable set. Therefore, a 0-1 variable y_j is defined for each node j . When $y_j = 1$, it means the node possesses an EVCS; when $y_j = 0$, it means there is no EVCS. c_j is the non-negative variable denoting EVCS capacity of each node j , subject to

$$c_j \leq y_j c_{max} \tag{3}$$

where c_{max} is the capacity limit. By this constraint, nodes without EVCS are forced $c_j = 0$. Therefore, the original Item (2) is equal to

$$\sum_{j \in N} (r_0 y_j + r_1 c_j) \tag{4}$$

where N denotes the set of all nodes.

In Item (3), function $t_k(x_k)$ denotes the time waiting and charging in an EVCS. The function shares a similar structure as $t_a(x_a)$, defined by

$$t_k(x_k) = t_k^0 (1 + 0.15(x_k/c_k)^4) \tag{5}$$

where t_k^0 is the charging time of a single vehicle without queuing. x_k is the number of vehicles in the EVCS while c_k is the EVCS capacity.

In Item (4), w represents an O-D pair, while W is the collection of all O-D pairs. p represents a path, while \tilde{p}^w is the collection of all possible paths connecting O-D pair w . $C_{p,w}^{ch}$ denotes the charging electricity cost of path p between O-D pair w . $t_{p,w}^{ch}$ denotes the charging time of path p between O-D pair w . $f_{p,w}$ is the traffic flow of path p between O-D pair w .

The objective mentioned above subjects to the following constraints:

$$x_a = \sum_{w \in W} \sum_{p \in \tilde{p}^w} f_{p,w} \tilde{\delta}_{p,w,a}, \forall a \in A \quad (6)$$

$$x_k = \sum_{w \in W} \sum_{p \in \tilde{p}^w} f_{p,w} \tilde{\sigma}_{p,w,k}, \forall k \in K \quad (7)$$

$$d^w = g_w(c_w), \forall w \in W \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{p \in \tilde{p}^w} f_{p,w} = d^w, \forall w \in W \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq d^w \leq d_{\max}^w, \forall w \in W \quad (10)$$

$$f_{p,w} \geq 0, \forall p, w \quad (11)$$

$$p_k^{dc} = \sum_{w \in W} \sum_{p \in \tilde{p}^w} f_{p,w} F_k^{p,w}, \forall k \in K \quad (12)$$

where constraints 6 and 7 illustrate the relationship between the path flow $f_{p,w}$ and the flow on link a and that which culminates at EVCS k , respectively. $\tilde{\delta}_{p,w,a}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_{p,w,k}$ are binary parameters indicating whether the path flow $f_{p,w}$ traverses link a and charges at EVCS k , respectively.

The all possible paths of an O-D pair is finite and thus the problem must have a solution. However, traversing all the possible paths are time-consuming. Therefore, the path generation algorithm proposed in [1] is utilized for selecting better paths. Besides, there are also PDN constraints based on DistFlow with angle and conic relaxations. The specific constraints are recorded in [2].

6 Comparison model for continuous planning

A DRL model is constructed for multi-period planning based on Soft Actor-Critic algorithm, in order to compare with the proposed framework based on LLM. The algorithm details are shown below:

6.1 Observation and Action Space

Since it is usually unnecessary to take action on each node and station in one action, feeding the entire topological graph into a DRL agent is highly inefficient and significantly increase difficulty of training. Therefore, a top K mechanism is adopted. At each decision step, the environment evaluates and selects the top $K/2$ most critical existing stations base on high utilization and profits, and the top $K/2$ most critical empty nodes based on traffic flow and origin-destination demands.

The observation space contains three components:

1. Station features: utilization rates, profit, capacity, and type.
2. Node features: origin, destination, passage counts, and user queries.
3. Global features: current budges, simulation week, total vehicle volume, and maintenance costs.

For each station, a discrete action is allowed, from removing five chargers to adding five chargers, which has 11 possible actions. For each empty node, the action space is similar but removing chargers is invalid. Therefore, the model possesses a multi-discrete action space. Besides, to lower the action space, only EVs are included in the DRL-based case so that all the station constructed are EVCSs.

6.2 Reward Function Design And Action Filtering

The reward function is meticulously shaped to balance profitability and service quality. The base reward is derived from the normalized weekly operational profit. To mitigate traffic congestion, a penalty is applied when the average utilization rate exceeds a critical threshold indicating severe queuing. Conversely, an under-utilization penalty is introduced to avoid wasted investments in idle stations. Furthermore, if an action results in budget deficits causing bankruptcy, the episode is terminated immediately with a severe terminal penalty of -100 .

Besides, it is worth noting how the DRL baseline handles infeasible actions like shrinking a non-existent station. Since the unconstrained hybrid action space is vast and the physical/financial constraints are exceptionally strict, the vast majority of the actions explored by the agent initially are inevitably invalid. According to our test, if explicit negative rewards were assigned to these infeasible actions, the dense penalty signals would overwhelm the sparse positive rewards generated by successful planning. Consequently, the DRL agent would rapidly learn to consistently choose “No Operation” simply to avoid penalties. To circumvent this, the baseline employs a silent action-filtering mechanism. Invalid actions are merely ignored or truncated to fit the constraints without imposing direct step penalties. For instance, when the expansion scheme is over-budget, some of them will be canceled silently. Thus, the agent is evaluated purely on the actual environmental feedback of the valid portion of its executed plan. This helps the agent converge to a more active strategy instead of inaction.

6.3 Network Architecture and Training

Handling a hybrid action space within neural networks presents a mathematical challenge: the hybrid action space does not support the standard practice of either discrete space or continuous space. To address this, the actor network employs the Gumbel-Softmax trick, a mathematical approximation that renders the discrete action selection smooth and differentiable during training, while still outputting a definitive categorical choice for the discrete part in practice. Meanwhile, the continuous part still employs the standard practice of reparameterization. Consequently, the stable gradient updates are ensured for the hybrid action space by the unification in the continuous space.

For the critic network evaluating the decision quality, entity encoders are designed for stations and empty nodes respectively. All the stations share the same parameter of station entity encoder while all the empty nodes share the same parameter of node entity encoder, the two separate encoders act as dedicated sub-networks to extract meaningful patterns from each type of object. Subsequently, an average pooling layer combines the feature from the two encoders, enabling the agent to grasp the holistic state of the coupled TN-PDN system and output a global state-action value.

For training efficiency, an asynchronous distributed architecture is implemented. Multiple CPU-based workers concurrently interact with the mesoscopic simulation environments to collect experiences and test the agent performance. To bootstrap the learning process and prevent premature convergence to sub-optimal actions, a heuristic rule-based policy with ϵ -greedy exploration is utilized to fill the replay buffer with high-quality initial experiences, since completely arbitrary actions are very likely to be infeasible. Concurrently, a central GPU-based learner continuously samples from the shared buffer to update the actor and critic networks, periodically synchronizing the latest parameters back to the workers.

7 Evolution of Stations in 5 years

The number of vehicles during the planning horizon exhibits a clear transportation electrification trend. As shown in the table of vehicle numbers in the main document, the number of EVs continuously increases from 750 to 1841 over 60 months, corresponding to a growth rate of approximately 145%. In contrast, gasoline vehicles (GVs) initially increase slightly and then gradually decline after Month 24. Specifically, the GV population rises from 4250 to a peak of 4425 before decreasing to 4052 at the end of the planning period. Meanwhile, the total number of vehicles still increases from 5000 to 5893, indicating that the transportation demand continues to expand during the transition process.

This evolution reveals a typical two-stage energy transition phenomenon. In the early stage, the growth of EVs mainly supplements newly emerging transportation demand, while conventional gasoline vehicles still dominate the system. Therefore, both charging and fueling infrastructures expand simultaneously to improve overall service coverage. However, after approximately Month 24, the EV penetration rate reaches 70%, and the system gradually enters a substitution stage in which EVs begin replacing gasoline vehicles. Consequently, the demand for public charging services increases rapidly, especially for fast charging facilities that support high-frequency and long-distance travel.

The spatial evolution of infrastructure deployment in Figure 1 is highly consistent with the vehicle composition changes. During the initial stage, charging stations and fueling stations are relatively evenly distributed across the network to guarantee basic accessibility. As EV penetration increases, charging facilities progressively concentrate around transportation hubs and high-centrality nodes, such as Nodes 5, 6, 23, 30, and 31. These nodes are typically located at major intersections or regions with high traffic flow, making them more suitable

(a) Month 0

(b) Month 12

(c) Month 24

(d) Month 36

(e) Month 48

(f) Month 60

Figure 1: Month 0 to 60 of continuous expansion of multi-type stations

for large-scale fast charging deployment. As a result, the charging network gradually evolves from a uniformly distributed structure into a polycentric hub-oriented topology.

In contrast, slow charging stations exhibit relatively moderate and spatially distributed growth because they mainly serve long-duration parking and residential charging demands. Fueling stations, although still preserved throughout the planning horizon, show significantly slower expansion due to the gradual decline of gasoline vehicle demand. This phenomenon reflects a realistic multi-energy coexistence stage during transportation electrification, in which charging infrastructure rapidly expands while traditional fueling infrastructure remains necessary for supporting the remaining gasoline vehicle population.

8 Test result details: LLM versus UE

Here are the details about the ablation experiment for LLM involving two factors:

1. With or without baseline values.
2. Default initial layout or UE initial layout

Table 7: Comparison with UE Model (With baseline, with UE initial layout)

Index	LLM 1	LLM 2	LLM 3	UE
Q	0.0001	<u>0.0000</u>	0.0007	0.3072
E	0.5295	0.5385	0.5347	<u>0.5520</u>
β	0.0089	<u>0.0000</u>	0.0080	0.0269
Investment/yuan	73.09M	70.49M	<u>64.66M</u>	67.95M
Monthly Profit/yuan	1.97M	1.94M	<u>1.98M</u>	1.92M
Payback Period/yrs	3.10	3.03	<u>2.73</u>	2.95
ROI	0.3227	0.3298	<u>0.3667</u>	0.3393
Iterations	12	7	7	-

Table 8: Comparison with UE Model (With baseline, without UE initial layout)

Index	LLM 1	LLM 2	LLM 3	UE
Q	0.0012	0.0003	0.0004	0.3072
E	0.5336	0.5423	0.5398	0.5520
β	0.0124	0.0089	0.0134	0.0269
Investment/yuan	71.02M	64.08M	69.09M	67.95M
Monthly Profit/yuan	1.96M	1.98M	1.93M	1.92M
Payback Period/yrs	3.02	2.70	2.98	2.95
ROI	0.3314	0.3700	0.3355	0.3393
Iterations	18	11	17	-

Table 9: Comparison with UE Model (Without baseline, with UE initial layout)

Index	LLM 1	LLM 2	LLM 3	UE
Q	0.0007	0.0004	0.0012	0.3072
E	0.5456	0.5323	0.5295	0.5520
β	0.0779	0.0000	0.0667	0.0269
Investment/yuan	70.55M	78.40M	78.53M	67.95M
Monthly Profit/yuan	1.92M	1.94M	1.94M	1.92M
Payback Period/yrs	3.06	3.37	3.38	2.95
ROI	0.3268	0.2971	0.2963	0.3393
Iterations	19	17	28	-

Table 10: Comparison with UE Model (Without baseline, without UE initial layout)

Index	LLM 1	LLM 2	LLM 3	UE
Q	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.3072
E	0.5332	0.5367	0.5335	0.5520
β	0.0214	0.0188	0.0230	0.0269
Investment/yuan	94.87M	107.82M	123.69M	67.95M
Monthly Profit/yuan	1.87M	1.80M	1.73M	1.92M
Payback Period/yrs	4.22	4.98	5.97	2.95
ROI	0.2367	0.2007	0.1674	0.3393
Iterations	19	23	30	-

To investigate the impact of two key design choices—whether to inject baseline values into the system prompt and whether to initialize the network with the UE layout—a factorial ablation experiment was conducted. Four configurations were evaluated: (1) with baseline and with UE initial layout (Table 7), (2) with baseline and without UE initial layout (Table 8), (3) without baseline and with UE initial layout (Table 9), and (4) without baseline and without UE initial layout (Table 10). For each configuration, three independent LLM runs were performed to account for randomness. The evaluation focuses on three system metrics—queue rate (Q), efficiency index (E), and power shedding ratio (β), where lower Q , higher E , and lower β are desirable. Economic indicators are also utilized, including total investment, monthly profit, payback period, and return on investment (ROI).

The baseline used is listed below, translated from Chinese:

Average queue rate: ≤ 0.0050
 Proportion of load shedding in the distribution network: ≤ 0.0100
 Total investment: $\leq 70,000,000$ (70M)
 Monthly profit: $\geq 1,900,000$ (1.9M)
 Payback period: ≤ 2.95 years
 Return on Investment: ≥ 0.31

8.1 Effect of Baseline Injection

Comparing configurations with and without baseline injection reveals a pronounced performance gap. When baseline values are provided (Tables 7 and 8), the LLM consistently achieves high ROI (0.3227–0.3700) and short payback periods (2.70–3.10 years). The best-performing LLM run (LLM 3 in Table 7) attains an ROI of 0.3667 and a payback period of only 2.73 years, outperforming the UE baseline (ROI 0.3393, payback 2.95 years). In contrast, when baseline values are absent (Tables 9 and 10), LLM performance deteriorates significantly. Total investment balloons to as high as 123.69M yuan (Table 10), payback periods extend to 4–6 years, and ROI drops to as low as 0.1674. Moreover, convergence slows considerably, with iteration counts increasing from 7–18 to 17–30. These results demonstrate that baseline injection provides a critical performance anchor, without which the LLM lacks explicit targets and tends to over-invest while failing to achieve competitive returns.

8.2 Effect of UE Initial Layout

The influence of initializing the network with the UE layout is conditional on the presence of baseline values. When baseline values are already provided (comparing Table 7 vs. Table 8), the UE initial layout has marginal impact: both configurations yield comparable ROI, investment, and payback periods, though the version with UE initialization requires slightly fewer iterations (7–12 vs. 11–18). However, when baseline values are absent (comparing Table 9 vs. Table 10), the UE initial layout serves as a crucial soft anchor. Without it, the LLM’s performance collapses into extreme over-investment and poor ROI (0.1674–0.2367); with it, even without baseline, the LLM manages to maintain moderate performance (ROI 0.2963–0.3268). This indicates that the UE initial layout and baseline injection share overlapping functionality—both provide reference benchmarks—but the latter is more effective while the former acts as a safety net when the latter is absent.

8.3 System Metrics Across Configurations

Across all four ablation configurations, the LLM consistently achieves near-zero queue rates ($Q \leq 0.0012$) and substantially lower power shedding ratios ($\beta \leq 0.0779$) compared to the UE baseline ($Q = 0.3072$, $\beta = 0.0269$).

This verifies that the LLM-based framework excels at reducing user waiting times and maintaining PDN stability regardless of the specific ablation setting. The efficiency index (E) of the LLM (0.5295–0.5456) slightly trails that of the UE baseline (0.5520) by approximately 1–2%, a marginal difference that is outweighed by the LLM’s superior economic performance.

8.4 Summary of Ablation Findings

The ablation study yields three main conclusions. First, baseline injection is the dominant factor driving planning quality; its absence leads to investment outrage and economic underperformance. Second, the UE initial layout acts as a conditional safeguard, most valuable when baseline guidance is unavailable. Third, the recommended configuration for practical deployment is to provide both baseline values and the UE initial layout (Table 7), which achieves the best overall economic performance and the fastest convergence (as few as 7 iterations).

9 Test result details: LLM versus DRL

Here is the curve of DRL training. It is quite difficult for the DRL agent to converge. Due to the limited time and device performance, it is not continued over 14000 samples.

References

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